

BIOFUEL FROM ALGAE: A REVIEW

V. Sridevi*, P. A. Satyanarayana¹ and Lenin Kumar B²

*Professor, Department of Chemical Engineering, Andhra University.

¹Research Scholar, Department of Chemical Engineering, Andhra University.

²Research Scholar, Department of Biotechnology, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University, Etcherla.

Article Received on 08/07/2015

Article Revised on 02/08/2015

Article Accepted on 26/08/2015

***Correspondence for**

Author

V. Sridevi

Professor, Department of
Chemical Engineering,
Andhra University.

ABSTRACT

Biodiesel assembly from algae has been beheld as all-important attributable to the claim for abuse abatement. Ecology issues can added and added affirm artefact adjustment and action acceptability and drive the next bearing of bread-and-butter opportunity. Some countries, are announcement blooming technologies that will be appeal common in

the advancing decades. The absolute activity appeal of our planet is accretion with citizenry advance admitting the deposit ammunition affluence are abbreviating swiftly. Biodiesel produced from biomass is broadly advised to be one of the a lot of acceptable alternatives to deposit fuels and a applicable agency for activity aegis and ecology and bread-and-butter sustainability. But as a ample breadth of abundant acreage is appropriate to breed biodiesel bearing earthbound plants, it may advance appear aliment absence and deforestation. Microalgae accept array of characteristics that acquiesce the assembly concepts of biodiesel which are decidedly added acceptable than their alternatives. Microalgae acquire top biomass productivity, oils with top lipid content, quick advance rates, accident of utilizing bordering and barren land, able of growing in alkali baptize and decay streams, and able of utilizing solar ablaze and CO₂ gas as nutrients.

KEYWORDS: Biodiesel, algae, green technology, microalgae, CO₂.

INTRODUCTION

Growing earthbound crops for biofuel may accomplish a negligible accession to net greenhouse gas emissions.^[1, 2] and may could could could cause added ecology impacts while abbreviation freshwater assets and aliment aegis.^[3] Given these limitations there has been

renewed / added absorption in amphibian and abyssal assembly for biofuels.^[4,5] This absorption can be disconnected into two principal components: biofuels acquired from macroalgae (seaweed) and biofuels acquired from microalgae (single corpuscle plants). Microalgal acquired biofuels accept accustomed abundant absorption as a antecedent for biodiesel.^[6-7] about assembly costs are an adjustment of consequence too big-ticket.^[3] Although there is currently astronomic analysis investment into the aggregate assembly of microalgae for biodiesel, photo bioreactors are absurd to be economically aggressive for bioenergy production, and adeptness in alfresco ponds is alone ill-fitted to regions with a about top bulk of sunlight hours and even again may still be uncompetitive in the biofuels bazaar.^[8]

Algae are a ample and assorted accumulation of simple plantlike organisms, alignment from unicellar to multicellar forms. These beef accept the adeptness to catechumen carbon dioxide to biomass that can added be candy after to aftermath biodiesel, fertilizer and added advantageous products. Photosynthetic advance of algae requires carbon dioxide, baptize and sunlight. Temperature should be in the ambit of 20–30_C in adjustment to accept acceptable growing conditions. Algae aswell charge added asleep nutrients like phosphorus and nitrogen in adjustment to grow. The actuality that micro algae abound in aqueous suspensions, allows for added able admission to H₂O, CO₂ and added nutrients which explains the abeyant for the assembly of added oil per assemblage breadth than added crops currently used. The actinic agreement of algae differs based on species. Algae accept several characteristics that could could could cause them to be a applicant biodiesel feedstock that deserves austere investigation.

In the endure two decades, growing all-embracing affair about the abrogating ecology appulse of deposit activity has fatigued cogent absorption to renewable aqueous biodiesel as a way to alter petroleum-based fuels.^[9] Biodiesel assembly about will be afflicted by prices, costs and abeyant allotment compared to application the acreage over recourses in added ways. First the accommodation to abound oilseed rather than added crops will be afflicted by the befalling bulk of land, appropriately demography annual of bazaar prices for seed, oilseed oil for the biodiesel markets, comestible oil and meal.^[10] Biomass is one of the bigger sources of energy.^[11] Large-scale accession of biomass activity could accord to acceptable development on several fronts, environmentally, socially and economic.^[12] Biodiesel (monoalkyl esters) is one of such addition fuel, which is acquired by the transesterification of

triglyceride oil with monohydric alcohols. It has been well-reported that biodiesel acquired from canola and soybean, palm, sunflower oil, algal oil as a agent ammunition substitute.^[13,14] Biodiesel is a controllable and biodegradable addition ammunition that is acquired from renewable sources. Biodiesel ammunition can be able from decay affable oil, such as palm, soybean, canola, rice bran, sunflower, coconut, blah oil, angle oil, craven fat and algae.^[15] which would partly abatement the annex on petroleum-based fuel. Biodiesel is a renewable and cleaner than petroleum based agent if it comes to CO₂ emissions. It can be apparent as renewable because of its agent from accustomed products, such as altered vegetable oils, beastly fats and algae. Biodiesel contains continued alternation alkyl esters and can be acclimated authentic or alloyed with petroleum based agent in a lot of agent engines after any modifications. Biodiesel is controllable and biodegradable and alone contains actual baby amounts of sulfur and ambrosial compounds.^[16]

Macroalgae accept been appear to accommodate added than 2400 accustomed articles of bartering accent in pharmaceutical, biomedical, and nutraceutical industries.^[17] Biodiesel is non-toxic, readily biodegradable and access atrocity of agent fuels. Agent engines are broadly acclimated as adeptness sources in average and able applications because it has lower ammunition consumption, carbon monoxide (CO) and hydrocarbons (HC) discharge if compared to added gasoline engines.^[18] The use of cars all over the apple abnormally in big cities and towns accord the a lot of in breeding aerial emission, appropriately could could cause the abuse of environment. Exhaust discharge of agent engines operating on accurate biodiesel and its blends with agent ammunition accept been appear in abundant studies.^[19] Abounding advisers investigate that access in the allotment of biodiesel in blends will abate the CO, SO_x, HC, chapped bulk (PM) discharge and smoke. However, the discharge of NO_x depends on the biodiesel sources.^[20]

Biodiesel is a accumulation of blubbery methyl- esters produced by a transesterification acknowledgment amid blubbery acids (triglyceride) and booze in attendance of a agitator,^[27] e.g.,

where R represents blubbery acids chains.^[28] Blubbery acids (FA) acclimated in biodiesel assembly appear from beastly fat or vegetal oil. One of the better challenges in biodiesel assembly is award acceptable feedstock able of affair the demand. Both oil and booze are

extracted from aliment crops such as corn, canola, soybean, palm, etc. In aftereffect this action is breach a aliment crop to be an activity crop. There is already an access bounce of aliment for bio-fuel. The United Nations (UN), for instance, is cogent a able disapproval of application aliment crops for bio-fuel, which they accept to be the key in foods bulk access and aliment shortage, although none of these crops could aftermath abundant oil to be adapted in biodiesel able to accommodated common demand.

The biodiesel from edi- ble oils is aswell not a acceptable advantage due to abundant antagonism with berry plants and accordingly, non-edible oils like *Jatropha*, *Pongamia*, *Neam* oils etc. are ac- corded top antecedence for biodiesel assembly in India. The plantations of *Jatropha curcas* are beneath agronomics on ample acreage breadth in the country and hopes are aloft for acceptable availability of oil for about-face to biodiesel. Apart from these non-edible oil resources, microalgae is aswell acceptable the focus as approaching antecedent of biodiesel as these are begin awfully affluent in oil that can be con-verted to biodiesel application absolute technology. Microalgae are prokaryotic (e.g. *Cyanobacteria*, *Cyanophyceae*) or eukaryotic (e.g. blooming algae) and diatoms (*Bacillario- phyta*) that can abound rapidly and reside in acrid altitude due to their unicellular or simple multicellular anatomy.^[21,22]

The arch investment for an algae biomass activity may be breach into the costs associated with algal biomass growth, agriculture i.e. abreast of the biomass from the culture, dewatering or absorption of algae to a acceptable akin for added processing, and algal oil abstraction systems. In addition, there are added acceptable activity costs such as engineering, permitting, basement preparation, antithesis of plant, accession and integration, and architect fees. Added to these, there are O&M costs which cover costs for nutrients (generally N-P-K), CO₂ distribution, and baptize bushing due to evaporative losses, utilities, apparatus replacement, and labour costs. In accession to basic and O&M costs, addition cogent bulk is appear the costs of the acreage or leasing.

Microalgae accept the abeyant to aftermath 5,000-15,000 gallons of biodiesel per acre per year. However, there are some challenges, including, top crop of algae biomass with top lipid agreeable and an able address to autumn the developed algae, to abstract the algal oil and transesterify the oil to biodiesel. Agriculture and isolating articles from micro algae cultures is one of the a lot of ambiguous areas of algal biofuel assembly technology. Oil accretion from agriculture and abstraction systems represents a ample claiming and even application

the a lot of advantageous microalgal species, absolute about 50% dry weight as oil, assembly amounts are actual low. How to accomplish this accretion action economically is one of the greatest challenges for biofuel assembly from microalgae. A biorefinery access to assembly should appropriately be considered. Articles acquired from microalgal biomass can cover article abstracts destined for a ambit of actinic products, such as, pharmaceuticals and belvedere chemicals, including, added fuels by about-face to booze and methane.^[23,24]

The capital cold of application biofuel is to balance carbon dioxide emissions. With the advance of analysis and development into new activity forms, biofuel is anticipation of as an able and applied addition carriage ammunition that may, in the future, play a cogent role in the abridgement of busline accompanying CO₂ emissions. The accessible technologies for CO₂ abduction cover bang into abysmal oceans or geological formations, physicochemical adsorption and added biological fixation. Abiotic methods, such as absolute bang of CO₂ into the Abysmal Ocean or geological formations poses cogent challenges like top amplitude requirements and abeyant arising with time.^[25] The adsorbent abstracts acclimated in physicochemical adsorption processes are by itself nonrenewable, big-ticket and it is difficult to ascendancy such process. One of the environmentally acceptable way to abate the carbon botheration is carbon aloofness i.e., to abate greenhouse gas emissions associated with activity production. Carbon aloofness is primarily a carbon bore which transforms carbon into a chemically and biologically abiding anatomy that can be stored.^[26]

Biofuel can be produced from assorted sources, but crop estimates are decidedly college for algae than for any added crop. This has consider-able implications for land-area requirements: algae able on alone 30 actor hectares and acquiescent biofuel at a bourgeois appraisal of 40,000 litres per hectare per year is acceptable to alter the 1,200 billion litres of petroleum acclimated by the world's better customer of petroleum, the United States. The breadth is agnate to that acclimated for soya burying in the United States (about 29 actor hectares) and about alert that acclimated for the US assembly of blah booze (about 14 actor hectares was acclimated to aftermath about 64 billion litres of booze in 2011), or an breadth about the admeasurement of New Mexico. Furthermore, algal agronomics can use the ample bulk of non-arable acreage accessible for development after displacing aliment production, and its about top appeal for baptize can be met by application low-quality sources such as decay or alkali water. Algae are about ideal as bacilli for developing the awful produc-tive and able-bodied crop strains that are capital for economically applicable biofuel production.

The seek for these strains can accomplish the all-inclusive assortment of algae, alignment from behemoth multicellular kelps to single-celled microalgae. Microalgae accept been the focus of acute biofuel production efforts because of the ease, calibration and acceleration at which they can be developed and manipulated, but strains alter decidedly in lipid profile, photosynthetic ability, advance rate, advance average claim (from acute halophilic to abyssal and beginning water), attrition to bacilli and biomass productivity. Although a lot of algae are phototrophs, abounding can be developed heterotrophically.

CONCLUSION

Renewable biofuels are bare to displace petroleum acquired carriage fuels, which accord to all-around abating and are of bound availability. Biodiesel is abeyant renewable fuels that accept admiring the a lot of attention. Biodiesel from microalgae seems to be the alone renewable biofuel that has the abeyant to absolutely displace petroleum-derived carriage fuels after abnormally affecting accumulation of aliment and added crop products. Microalgal biodiesel is potentially another acceptable blooming energy. It is accessible to aftermath microalgal biodiesel to amuse the fast growing activity appeal aural the restraints of acreage and baptize resources. Microalgal agriculture can be accompanying with flue gas CO₂ acknowledgment and wastewater treatment. Microalgae can aftermath a ample array of atypical byproducts. Microalgal biodiesel is not yet economically applicable abundant to alter petroleum based fuels or attempt with added renewable activity technologies such as wind, solar, geothermal and added forms of Bioenergy. Despite their top abeyant both in agreement of abundance and sustainability, a lot of algae based biofuel concepts still crave cogent investment to become commercially viable.

REFERENCES

1. Scharlemann JPW, Laurance WF: Environmental science - How green are biofuels? *Science.*, 2008; 319: 43–44.
2. Gibbs HK, Johnston M, Foley JA, Holloway T, Monfreda C, Ramankutty N, Zaks D: Carbon payback times for crop-based biofuel expansion in the tropics: the effects of changing yield and technology. *Environ Res Lett.* 2008. 3. doi:10.1088/1748-9326/3/3/034001.
3. Shilton A, Guieysse B: Sustainable sunlight to biogas is via marginal organics. *Curr Opin Biotechnol.*, 2010; 21: 287–291.

4. Singh J, Cu S: Commercialization potential of microalgae for biofuels production. *Renew Sust Energ Rev.*, 2010; 14: 2596–2610.
5. Williams PJJ, Laurens LML: Microalgae as biodiesel & biomass feedstocks: review & analysis of the biochemistry, energetics & economics. *Energy Environ Sci.*, 2010; 3: 554–590.
6. Brennan L, Owende P: Biofuels from microalgae-a review of technologies for production, processing, and extractions of biofuels and co-products. *Renew Sust Energ Rev.*, 2010; 14: 557–577.
7. Mata TM, Martins AA, Caetano NS: Microalgae for biodiesel production and other applications: a review. *Renew Sust Energ Rev.*, 2010; 14: 217–232.
8. Wilcox HA: The U.S. Navy's Ocean food and energy farm project. In *Book the U.S. Navy's Ocean food and energy farm project*. Edited by Monney NT. 83–104., 1977; 83–104.
9. Huntley ME, Redalje DG. CO₂ mitigation and renewable oil from photosynthetic microbes: a new appraisal. *Mitigation Adapt Strateg Global Change.*, 2007; 12: 573-608.
10. Frohlich A and Rice B. Evaluation of *Camelina sativa* oil as a feedstock for biodiesel production. *Ind Crops Products.*, 2005; 21: 25-31.
11. Kulkarni, M.G. and A.K. Dalai. Waste cooking oil-an economical source for biodiesel: A review. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, 2006; 45: 2901-2913.
12. Turkenburg W.C. Renewable energy technologies. In: Goldemberg, J. (Ed). *World Energy Assessment, Preface*. United Nations Development Programme, New York, USA. 2000. pp: 219-272.
13. Lang, X., A.K. Dalai, N.N. Bakhshi, M.J. Reaney and P.B. Hertz. Preparation and characterization of biodiesels from various Bio- Oils. *Bioresour. Technol.*, 2002; 80: 53-62.
14. Spolaore, P., C. Joannis-Cassan, E. Duran and A. Isambert. Commercial applications of microalgae. *J. Biosci. Bioeng.*, 2006; 101: 87-96.
15. Sharif, A.B.M.H, A.B. Nasrulhaq, H.A.M., Majid, S. Chandran and R. Zuliana. Biodiesel production from waste cooking oil as environmental benefits and recycling process. *A Review. Asia Biofuel Conference Book*. Dec., 2007; 11-13.
16. Körbitz, W. Biodiesel production in Europe and North America, an encouraging prospect', *Renewable Energy.*, 1999; 16: 1-4.
17. Saranya C, Girija K, Estimation of major pigment content in seaweeds collected from Pondicherry coast, *The Experiment.*, 2013; 9(1): 522-525.

18. Hasimoglu C, Ciniviz M, Ozsert I, Icingur Y, Parlak A, Salman MS, Performance characteristics of a low heat rejection diesel engine operating with biodiesel, *Renew Energy.*, 2008; 33: 1709–1715.
19. Kassaby MEL, Allah MAN, Studying the effect of compression ratio on an engine fuelled with waste oil produced biodiesel/diesel fuel *Alexandria Engineering Journal.*, 2013; 52(1): 1–11
20. Ahmed AS, Khan S, Hamdan S, Rahman R, Kalam A, Masjuki HH, Mahlia TMI, Biodiesel Production from Macro Algae as a Green Fuel for Diesel Engine, *Journal of Energy & Environment.*, 2010; 2 (1): 1-5.
21. Li Y, B. Wang, N. Wu and C. Q. Lan, “Effects of Nitrogen Sources on Cell Growth Andlipid Production of *Neochloris oleoabundans*,” *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology.*, 2008; 81(4): 629-636.
22. Li Y, M. Horsman, N. Wu, C. Q. Lan and N. Dubois- Calero, “Biofuels from Microalgae,” *Biotechnology Prog- ress.*, 2008; 24(4): 815-820.
23. Tredici M. Processes, projects and prospects of algae biofuels. In, *Fuels of the Future 2012, 9th BBE/UFOP International Congress on Biofuels.*, 2012; 23-24.
24. Molina-Grima, E., E.H. Belarbi, F.G. Ación Fernández, A. Robles Medina and Y. Chisti. Recovery of microalgal biomass and metabolites: process options and economics. *Biotechnology advances.*, 2003; 20 (7–8): 491-515.
25. Lackner K.S. A guide to CO₂ sequestration. *Science.*, 2003; 300: 1677-1678.
26. Chang T.H., Su H.M. and Chiu C.L. Value-at-risk estimation with the optimal dynamic biofuel portfolio. *Energy Economics.*, 2011; 33: 264-272.
27. Wilson, R. and I.H. Farag. “Parametric Study of Biodiesel Quality and Yield Using a Bench-Top Processor.” *International Journal of Oil, Gas and Coal Technology.*, 2012; 5(1): 92-105.
28. Knothe, Gerhard. *The Biodiesel Handbook*. AOCS press, Champaign, Illinois, 2005.